

The following artifacts are provided as part of the artifact evaluation process to demonstrate our claims and support reproducibility:

1. **Interview Recruitment Messages** – Includes the text used for participant recruitment in the interview study.
2. **Consent Form** – We used the version available at the time of the study, in accordance with the University's data protection policy, and submitted the important details for your reference.
3. **Interview Questions (English, Urdu)** – To support the reproducibility of our study we added all three language versions of the interview guide (the English version is added in Appendix A of the paper)
4. **Interview Protocol (English, Urdu)** – Contains the script used at the beginning of each interview session, including the introduction, explanation of study purpose, and participant rights.